

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ Lyme borreliosis_1_dog serology

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Serological surveillance of dogs in high-risk regions; testing for <i>Borrelia burgdorferi s.l.</i> (1).
2	Surveillance aim	Detection of a change of prevalence; detection of a change of the geographic distribution.
3	Target species and group	Domestic dogs. (2; 3)
4	Target sector / production type	All dogs; preferably dogs with exposure to areas of probable exposure to vectors (<i>Ixodes</i>), such as hunting dogs, dogs living in proximity of forests, etc.
5	Geographical area covered	Areas where the disease is already endemic; adjacent areas for surveillance of geographic distribution; areas with high <i>Ixodes</i> presence and strong human utilisation (parks, recreational areas).
6	Age group	All ages.
7	Sampling point and strategy	At public and private facilities capable of correct blood sampling and processing, on voluntary or mandatory basis, continuous or limited in time. A representative sample should be defined by each MS based on the dog population and history of disease prevalence in a given area.
8	Sampling time period	Acute infections are more likely to be detected from March to November, considering the period of maximum incidence of the disease in humans (4). However, (1) the active period tick vector varies depending on the latitude, altitude and the actual temperature, and (2) serology doesn't target active infections but gives an account on historic exposure. (4)
9	Sampling matrix	Whole blood. (5)
10	Type of disease indicators	Antibodies. Direct diagnosis has low sensitivity.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal.

12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Dogs sharing the same living human environment, which is considered at risk.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Indirect fluorescent antibody test; enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. C6 peptide-based assay to identify antibodies to <i>B. burgdorferi</i> is used in dogs (5).
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component contributes to case detection with high expected sensitivity (5). Infections with <i>B. burgdorferi</i> tend to persist and hence also antibody concentrations remain high (6). It can possibly serve to compare relative risks across geographical areas (given similar sampling strategies), but the sample is likely to be biased (non-random or non-representative) due to convenience sampling and therefore cannot be used to estimate the system sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Tick-borne encephalitis virus, Anaplasma phagocytophilum causing human granulocytic ehrlichiosis, Francisella tularensis causing Tularaemia, Rickettsia helvetica and Rickettsia monacensis, Babesia divergens and Babesia microti responsible for Babesiosis, Louping ill virus. (5)
18	References	<p>1) Johnson JL, Ginsberg HS, Zhioua E, Whitworth UG Jr, Markowski D, Hyland KE, Hu R. Passive tick surveillance, dog seropositivity, and incidence of human lyme disease. Vector Borne Zoonotic Dis. 2004 Summer;4(2):137-42. doi: 10.1089/1530366041210710. PMID: 15228814.</p> <p>2) Elhelw, R., Elhariri, M., Hamza, D. et al. Evidence of the presence of Borrelia burgdorferi in dogs and associated ticks in Egypt. BMC Vet Res 17, 49 (2021)</p> <p>3) Cook MJ, Puri BK. Estimates for Lyme borreliosis infections based on models using sentinel canine and human seroprevalence data. Infect Dis Model. 2020;5:871-888.</p>

		<p>4) Petrulionienė A, Radzišauskienė D, Ambrozaitis A, Čaplinskas S, Paulauskas A, Venalis A. Epidemiology of Lyme Disease in a Highly Endemic European Zone. <i>Medicina (Kaunas)</i>. 2020;56(3):115.</p> <p>5) WOHAE Borrelia Technical card - Borrelia spp. (Infection with) Aetiology Epidemiology Diagnosis Prevention and Control Potential Impacts of Disease Agent Beyond Clinical Illness References, Last updated 2020</p> <p>6) Straubinger, R. K., Summers, B. A., Chang, Y. F., & Appel, M. J. (1997). Persistence of Borrelia burgdorferi in experimentally infected dogs after antibiotic treatment. <i>Journal of clinical microbiology</i>, 35(1), 111-116.</p> <p>7) Miró, G., Wright, I., Michael, H. et al. Seropositivity of main vector-borne pathogens in dogs across Europe. <i>Parasites Vectors</i> 15, 189 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-022-05316-5</p>
19	Additional comments	<p>Antibody positivity was concentrated in Northern and Eastern Europe with higher rates of positivity (> 5%) in Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Slovenia, Sweden, and Switzerland and lowest rates (< 1%) in Andorra, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Romania, and Spain. Remaining countries had test positivity between 1 and 5%. The highest test positivity was seen in Sweden (13.3%) and lowest in Greece (< 0.1%). (7)</p>